

ATTRACTIVE METAPHORS AND METAPHORS USED IN THE WORK

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The use of metaphors, similes and pictorial means used in the works ensures wide consumption of the work. The events expressed in the work of art or the intended purpose of writing the work also depends on how visual means are used. Karimov cites such thoughts: "the writer's work on the word is his repeated review of the text in the process of creation, his work to make the plot, image, image and narrative effective" Any speech or The impressiveness of the artistic work is provided by unique visual expressions, artistic similes, metaphors, proverbs, proverbs and synonyms. In addition, the skill of the writer depends on it. Regarding the use of words, Zafar Umrkulov in his book "Erkin A'zam's skill of using words" cites the following points: becomes an artist. As a result of the artistic use of the word, in addition to the main function of the language, an artistic and aesthetic function is created. The source that fulfills such a function of language is fiction. Through his work, the writer not only talks

ABSTRACT

In the article, the forms of metaphors and similes, which are rarely used in our language, but attract attention when used in the language of artistic works, were discussed in detail. Metaphors are warmly received by readers as they expand the consumption of the work. The lexicon and figurative expressions of the Uzbek language are so rich that the metaphorical forms presented in the story "Tazarru" by Istam Hamrayev proved it.

about his wishes and events, but also shows the aesthetic beauty of his native language. That is, the language of an artistic work performs two different tasks. Vinograd makes the following comments about this in his lecture "The science of the language of fiction and its tasks", he emphasizes that the word "language" is used in two different meanings, i.e. 1) "speech" or "text" reflecting the system of one or another national language; 2) "language of art" is used in the sense of a system of artistic means of expression, and the writer reflects our nationality through the work. At the same time, it is related to linguistic and cultural studies.

Let's talk about the word metaphor at this point. This word is "a word or phrase used figuratively based on analogy or simile; gives the meaning of "metaphor, metaphor". Such migrations are also studied in depth in linguopoetics.

Our language is such a wide river, at the bottom of which there are many undiscovered corals. For this reason, I

decided to prove our opinion through the story "Tazarru" by Istam Hamroyev. Below we will get acquainted with unique examples of metaphors and similes used in the work.

To take under the wing. To take under one's wing means "1) to take under one's shelter, protection or care; 2) "to gather around" and in the play it means to take care: together with Gavhar, he took his daughter-in-law and nephews under his wing, they all ate from the same pot, and tried to keep their nephews on their feet as long as they could.

Wrap it up. In this case, it means to transfer the honor of the girl without saying a word, giving the meanings of "making a lot of goods and clothes and providing them with these (about the girl to be transferred, her wedding)". also gave her name: the eldest of her nieces is a girl, she was passed away two years ago.

Heart pounding. The noise in this is "noise, commotion; commotion; giving the meaning of гувур-гувур, and the meaning of ыгула fits in the combination, and expresses that a person is worried about something: The rider heard this news, and his heart began to rumble.

To cut one's heart. In this case, the word "ortamaq" means "1) to catch fire, to burn, to burn; 2) heat up to the final level; 3) cause mental suffering; giving the meanings of "to burn", the 3rd meaning in the dictionary is correct in the combination: the feeling of guilt in front of Gavhar was burning in his heart, and the thought of how to get rid of this anger did not give him peace.

Spend your whole life in front of your eyes. In this case, to pass before the eyes means "to look from one side and examine; "to look over" means to think about one's

past life one by one: The rider went out filled with the night and spent his whole life in front of his eyes one by one until morning.

To be sloppy. The word apok-chapak in this combination means "harmonious; The meaning of "friendly, friendly" is given as the meaning of mutual harmony: He enjoys fighting, sometimes he doesn't get hurt even if he gets punched a lot, but despite that, he doesn't hold any grudges in his heart. He was friendly and friendly.

Break the gate. In this compound, the word "break the gate" is close to the word "break the gate" and means "to come repeatedly, without stopping (about the suitors who come to the house of an adult girl): Gavhar is one of the leading girls of the village, and the suitors are the ones who break the gate" the violator was eighteen years old.

Put it on the body. This combination is "1) to pull out its weft in order to weave fabric; 2) to visit many times, to be a tourist somewhere" and the second meaning is mostly suitable for the text: He is very handsome, middle-aged, and because of his quickness of hands and feet, the suitors of the house like him. they put a sign on the door

Win a heart. This combination corresponds to the combination of "heart won" and gives the meaning of "not pulling, not being afraid": Yurak yutdi.

To take on the floor. In this case, the word "layer" means "every layer, layer of things and between them" and its meaning is given: Heavy-weight, poor-spoken, winter-summer mudom has a hoe on his shoulder, fathered eleven children during their life together, seven Mardon, the husband who always took his son to his

house and raised him to be a hard worker, did not interfere in his wife's affairs.

To be empty-handed. The word "empty" in it means "empty with nothing in it" and the meaning of the combination is expressed mainly to be void: In this case, Ikram did not chase after money, but money itself chased him. Due to his indefatigable work and his ever-increasing energy, he would go out with several partners until his hand was empty, and he would do well, while the others would restore one building, his gang would destroy two or three buildings.

To make a mistake. In this case, *istihol* means "andisha"; sense of judgment; to hesitate" and *istihola* means "to feel such a feeling" and is used in the play in the sense of to hesitate: After that, Chavandoz noticed that his wife sometimes cried at night without telling him, and he also did not know how to tell his mother-in-law's words to her husband. it would make him sick, and he would suffer worse.

The point is to stay stuck. In this case, *chatter* gives the meaning of "increasing chatter" and expresses the fact that the conversation is mainly spoken: Even when Muqaddam reached the age of fifty, Muqaddam was still chatting with this and that man in the village.

Pass in front of the dog. The meaning expressed in this is expressed in the meanings of to take away the reins, to give a slap. he used to leave his father too.

To run away. In this case, walking means "to walk quickly with a big step; to shake *lokkilamaq* (about the walking of horses and donkeys)" and the work gives the meaning of walking fast: - Bride, give this to me, give it to Gavhar, I gave her answer, she went to her father's house, he said, - he left his horse and ran away.

To knock vigorously. With the zeal in this "with all his soul, with all his strength; It is given the meaning of moving with all one's strength: after learning that his son was finally at home and that Oliya had run away, Bozorgul came to his mother's door and knocked with all his might. .

It is sharper than the sharper. In the dictionary, this word means "die young!" The guy is dead! Stay young!" meaning such things as, it is mainly used in the sense of cursing: "If Gavharimdi's son does not catch you, you will be cut off from your razor, young man," said the old woman, slapping her son on the face, and then left the gate.

Immersed in pleasure Immersion in this means "1) to sink into water or another liquid; take a bath 2) to enter between something, to hide, to disappear from sight, to go without being seen, to enter, and to indulge in pleasure is expressed: the same with Chavandoz Oliya, like when he once married Gavhar again plunged into pleasure.

He saw with his eyes open. This combination is expressed in the dictionary as the meaning of "first marriage (first husband or first wife)". Gavhar saw Jabborqul's eight-year-old school-going daughter and five-year-old son as if they were his own children.

It's as if something is broken from inside. Through this combination, it is expressed that he suddenly heard the news that he did not expect and that he fell into an uncomfortable situation: This phrase, after hearing that Chavandoz Gavhar had a child, he was confused, as if something had been cut off from him.

An explosion of thought. Exploding means "bursting into pieces due to the

rapid expansion of gases as a result of a strong reaction or ignition", and it is expressed as a sudden, quick, unexpected dream: No, it was not jealousy towards Gavhar, but this The thought that had been simmering in the net of his heart until now, which he probably did not want to admit with false pride, "maybe it's my fault," suddenly burst into his mind.

To go inside. In this case, this phrase means "1) to be hard-pressed, to be embarrassed; 2) to be oppressed by grief and envy, to be mentally tormented: Every time he heard that Gavhar had another child, he would get upset, because there was no cure for his pain, he would take his pain from alcohol, which not only hurt his mind, but also his body, because of his helplessness.

Let the cloth fall into the water. In this case, rags are "pieces of foreign goods, used, old-fashioned fabrics; 2) in general, yarn, things made from it; 3) silk fabric; 4) giving the meaning of "empty, empty, empty" in the work, this combination means the failure of the intended work: Before him, the rider's rag fell into the water and returned.

Burn the mind. Koyamik means "1) to say a reprimand, to say a word, to rebuke, to fight; 2) to check with malice, to inquire with malice, to try to destroy someone's reputation", and this combination is described in the work as a man's self-indulgence: He learned from the horseman's wife.

To cut one's heart. To burn in this means "1) to catch fire, to burn, to burn; 2) to heat up to the final level, to burn; 3) by giving the meaning of "to cause spiritual pain, to burn", the work gives the meaning of suffering spiritually through the combination: Yes, not every childless

woman can be like Gavhar, but the feeling of guilt in front of her hurts her heart.

Gnawing pain. To gnaw "1) to scrape and crush something hard with the teeth; 2) to torment, to torment (about mental experiences)" meaning the mental suffering of a person: But this was not all the bruises on the forehead of Chavandoz, whose marriage was broken a couple of times, and the pain of childlessness was gnawing at his heart.

It's like swallowing coals. In this case, the word "laqqa" means "1) a predatory fish that lives in fresh waters, has no scales, and has whiskers; 2) giving the meaning of "lahm, boneless meat", this combination in the work expresses that a person has swallowed a piece of coal, that is, an accidental situation occurred that he did not want: burned: the woman who was looking at Egamberdi unknowingly and flirtatiously was Oliya!

to leave In this case, to be surprised gives the meaning of "to be surprised": He recognized the beauty, it surprised him,

Pulling his heart behind him. This refers to a person's fear and danger of an event: Oliya Chavandoz's angry look at her made her realize that he was aware of everything, and now it was her turn.

To throw a stick in the eye. In this case, this phrase has the meaning of plotting: "I know the clan of this breed well, if he lives with you for a hundred years, when he dies, he will throw a stick in your eyes once, and if he is still there, he will answer this faceless bastard,

To walk in pieces. In this case, "1) willingly, deliberately, specially; 2) rostakami, assiduously, given the meaning of walking as one wants: If she stayed, she understood that it would be an

incomparable pain for her to stay at Chavandozni's, but leaving is even more difficult, because her husband has been in the army for so many years. If he left the place where he was walking, he couldn't know how he would be able to walk with his head held high.

Rub your nose on the ground. In this case, this expression gave the meaning of giving away: The rider achieved his goal, and the biggest reward for him in the race was that he rubbed Egamberdi's nose on the ground in front of so many people.

To be disappointed. In this case, frustration means "desire, desire for work, action, etc.;" giving the meaning of "enthusiasm" and expressing disappointment in a job in the combination: But now the Rider is completely disappointed in life,

To make a fuss. In this case, the word *tusmol* means "a suspicion made by oneself without knowing for sure; "guess" and "guess" meaning to guess: Oliyā knew that she had completely lost her previous attention in front of her husband, and she only guessed where and with whom he would spend the night.

To be beautiful. In this case, to cheer up means "to improve your mood": the rider cheered up a bit when he heard this, but he didn't even bother to take back a part of the money.

to smell In this case, this phrase means "to spread the word, to be revealed": Take away the rest for that, don't smell it

To soften the heart. In this case, this combination means "to pity; "to come down from bitterness, anger" has the meaning: the rider lightens up his sin in front of Gavhar, even if it is a little, and thus the old woman's heart is also somewhat relieved, so the heart softens.

To be kind. In this case, this combination gives the meaning of "awakening his affection" and shows that his heart has softened in the work: For thirty years, he has been harsh and unkind to him, and now he feels his love for his son, who is standing in front of him with pleading eyes like a young child.

Therefore, we must protect our language, protect it like the apple of our eye, prove its uniqueness and promote it to others. Through these articles, I wanted to show how rich our language is in words (vocabulary), phrases, figurative expressions, similes and metaphors. One of my goals in writing this article was to prove that our native language is not different from other languages, to introduce you to examples of unique and beautiful metaphors and similes in works of art. Attractive metaphors are also used in modern works. Also, the forms of movement used in Istam Hamroyev's short story "Tazarru" were noteworthy. I presented to you such migrations.

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